

THE ROLE OF ETHNOPSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. The family is where the foundations of a person's relationships with representatives of other ethnic communities are laid, and a great deal in people's lives depends on what these relationships will be like. It is in the family that, from an early age, a person becomes a bearer of traditions and habits, social and moral values of the nation to which he belongs. This article also examines the dynamics of the development of marital relations and their national specifics, the stages of the formation of marital and family relations.

Keywords: family, marital relations, marital and family relations, tradition, culture, stages of formation of marital and family relations.

INTRODUCTION

In our multi-ethnic state, interethnic marriages are a common phenomenon, and to know and then correctly understand the psychological characteristics of people in a multi-ethnic family is an important task for scientists and social workers. There are no exact statistics on this matter. In addition, the current national situation also has a negative impact on this problem. At the same time, it is quite obvious that the attractiveness of this type of marriage, as shown by individual studies, is quite high.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The institution of the family exists among all modern nations, and although it is surprisingly diverse, all nations understand the family as the only way to preserve an ethnic community. The family is a certain type of activity for which girls and boys are prepared from childhood. As special studies and practice show, the foundations of an individual's relationships with representatives of other ethnic communities are laid in the family, and a great deal in people's lives depends on what these relationships will be. It is in the family that, from an early age, a person becomes a bearer of traditions and habits, social and moral values of the nation to which he belongs. But in the case where several nationalities are involved in the family, this process is not sufficiently understood by society.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Often the historical roots of a people become the potential and the reference point for the creation of some historical traditions for the human race.

Let us consider the dynamics of the development of marital relations and their national specificity.

At the first stage of the formation of marital and family relations, the social-role and interpersonal adaptation to the conditions of family life, which is inherent for each ethnic community, usually occurs. This is the time of the initial entry into each other's spiritual world, mutual adaptation, distribution of social roles, as well as arrangements for everyday life and organization of recreation in a couple.

If there are representatives of different nationalities and peoples in the family, then the relationships in the family are often not smooth and even. This stage in the life of the young is very difficult and important, they need to constantly be with each other and understand the national costs of the traditions of each of them. In these relationships, only love ensures the stabilization of marital relations, sweeping away obstacles in its path.

At the second stage of the formation of marital relations, which begins after the birth of a child, there is a significant restructuring in the relationship of the spouses, associated with a change in the role structure, the emergence of parental responsibilities, the redistribution of material resources and the budget of time. At this stage, the process of establishing unity in common interests, issues related to the family. However, already at this time the basis for overcoming all kinds of disagreements, including nationally specific ones, appears, the prerequisites are laid for a general, international attitude of the spouses towards themselves and other people, a correct assessment of ethnic "shortcomings" and misunderstandings, if they take place.

The most important thing is that spouses are forced to think seriously about the international principles of upbringing in the family, connected not only with the birth of a child, but also with its development, with the future prospects of its behavior in culture, ethics.

The distribution of family responsibilities in the home is of great importance. For example, among the peoples of the Caucasus, a man begins to perform responsibilities around the house and yard only after the birth of a baby.

Special psychological studies show that young people of different nationalities, having fallen in love with each other and intending to get married, do not think seriously about the possible difficulties of living together (including interethnic ones) that await them.

Having encountered difficulties at the second and third stages of the formation of their family, they overcome them in different ways.

The third stage is characterized by a tendency toward sustainability and stability of marital relations in a number of key areas of family life. Social roles are fully distributed, and they cease to be a source of disagreement. A leader in each of the family functions is finally identified, if he was not previously determined in accordance with national traditions.

The fourth stage: a complete internationalization of intra-family relations occurs. Growing children not only effectively influence the performance of duties by spouses, but also have a corrective effect on their behavior. At the same time, during the period under consideration, spouses have more time for themselves, raising their cultural and intellectual level, and establishing intimate relationships.

The fifth stage is associated with the final stabilization of marital relations in all spheres of family life. Spouses establish closeness, and often complete unity of views on a significant number of problems. Adult children bring elements of democracy, obligation, meaningfulness of actions, and balanced decisions into the moral and psychological atmosphere of the family.

CONCLUSION

Often, mutual understanding, mutual assistance, mutual trust and tolerance take place in the actions of spouses. During this period, conflicts on interethnic grounds practically do not arise, spouses are fully adapted to each other's national traditions and characteristics.

References:

1. Batarchuk D.S. The problem of intra-family relations in interethnic marriages: socio-psychological and psychological-acmeological features // *Acmeology*, No. 3 (51), 2014. - P. 113-120.
2. Besayeva A.G., Ikoeva R.R., Gazzaeva M.Z. On the problem of ethnic family conflicts (psychological aspect) // *Problems of modern pedagogical education*, No. 63-4, 2019. P. 275-277.
3. Nabiullina A.V. Basic approaches and methodology for studying interethnic relations // *Scientific notes of Kazan University. Series Humanitarian sciences*, 151, No. 5-1, 2019. - P. 15-21.
4. www.ziyonet.uz

